

An Improved Synthesis of 2,5-Diethoxycarbonyl- 1,4-cyclohexane-dione

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In preparing the title compound, required in large amounts in connection with some other studies, we have encountered difficulty with the prescribed procedure¹. We have overcome the difficulty by adopting the procedure, described below, furnishing reproducible yields of 70-78% of the diethoxycarbonylcyclohexane-dione.

Procedure.—To a dispersion of sodium dust (2.7 g.) in benzene (30 ml) was added a solution of freshly distilled diethyl succinate (10 g.) in benzene (30 ml). Care was taken to exclude moisture in the usual way. The mixture was heated at 120-40° under reflux for 10 hr. in an oil bath. On cooling, absolute ethanol (1.6 ml) was added to it and the whole was heated again at 120-40° for 25 hr. On removing the solvent under reduced pressure, a brown solid was obtained, which was dissolved in ice-cold water (100 ml) and filtered quickly. The crude diethoxycarbonylcyclohexane-dione, obtained on acidifying the filtrate by HCl, was crystallised from ethanol (charcoal) in colorless needles (5.5 g.)*, m.p. 126°.

The authors' sincere thanks are due to Prof. R. C. Mehrotra for providing facilities in the laboratory and to the authorities of the University of Rajasthan for providing a scholarship to one of them (S. K. M.).

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Received May 15, 1964.

1. "Organic Reactions", Vol. I, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1957, p. 283.

*The yield mentioned is an average of those from several such lots.